

Reflective Portfolio Implementation in Clinical Clerkship: Evidence from medical education in a Small Island Developing State (Mauritius)

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Introduction

Background and context of clinical education

Clinical education is a cornerstone of medical training, offering students essential experience in patient care and the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world settings. In Mauritius, medical education is delivered through a five-year MBBS programme at the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, University of Mauritius, followed by a mandatory internship. The final three years of the programme involve immersive clinical clerkships in public hospitals, where students rotate through disciplines such as internal medicine, surgery, ENT, and paediatrics. This study was conducted during the 2022-2023 academic year, with portfolio implementation spanning one full academic year.

However, the Mauritian health system, like many in Small Island Developing States (SIDS), faces constraints such as high student-to-patient ratios, clinician shortages, and limited supervision due to overburdened healthcare staff. These systemic limitations result in students experiencing fragmented supervision and variable learning opportunities, which may impede their ability to integrate theory with practice and develop clinical confidence (Atkinson and Ajjawi, 2019; Monrouxe et al., 2014).

Furthermore, the cultural context of education in Mauritius is often shaped by hierarchical teacher-student relationships and exam-focused learning strategies, which may limit the use of open-ended, reflective educational tools. In such environments, learners may be less inclined to engage in critical self-evaluation unless explicitly encouraged and supported through structured pedagogical interventions (Bolton, 2014; Brookfield, 1995).

The role of reflective practice

To address these challenges, reflective practice has emerged as a foundational strategy in modern medical education. It allows students to critically assess their clinical encounters, identify learning gaps, and transform experiences into meaningful personal and professional

growth (Sandars, 2009). Reflective practice is a key element of adult learning theory, which promotes self-directed and experiential learning as mechanisms for effective development (Knowles, 1984; Moon, 2004).

As described by Mann et al. (2009), reflection fosters deeper learning and enables students to become more self-aware, adaptive, and critical in their approach to clinical practice. Reflective practice is frequently operationalized through reflective portfolios, which serve as structured tools allowing students to document, analyse, and learn from their experiences (Boud, Keogh and Walker, 1985; Moon, 2004).

Reflective portfolios typically consist of:

1. Reflective writing sections, where students critically analyse their encounters.
2. Mini-Clinical Evaluation Exercises (mini-CEX), for formative feedback on clinical and communication skills.
3. Direct Observation of Procedural Skills (DOPS) for performance-based assessment of technical procedures.

These tools promote self-assessment, critical thinking, and professional insight (Teunissen and Dornan, 2008). Recent studies have shown that reflective portfolios enhance clinical learning and help students transition into competent healthcare professionals by reinforcing habits of lifelong learning and continuous improvement (Er et al., 2019; Zubair and Bilal, 2018).

The reflective portfolio in clinical clerkships

The clinical clerkship phase marks the shift from classroom learning to the dynamic environment of hospital-based care. Reflective portfolios have gained prominence as mechanisms for helping students bridge this gap by promoting active engagement with clinical experiences (Davis et al., 2001; Pee et al., 2000). However, despite their potential, successful implementation depends on contextual relevance, user training, and adequate feedback mechanisms; factors that are often under-addressed in resource-constrained settings like Mauritius and other SIDS (Driessen et al., 2007).

This study investigates the development, implementation, and evaluation of a comprehensive reflective portfolio tailored to the clinical education context in Mauritius. Specifically, it explores how reflective portfolios support self-directed learning, professional development, and critical thinking among medical students in their clinical years; while also identifying barriers such as time constraints and limited feedback. By examining these issues within the Mauritian context, the study contributes new evidence to the sparse literature on reflective

practices in SIDS and offers implications for wider applicability in similar resource-limited healthcare education systems.

Aims and objectives

This study aims to evaluate the impact of reflective portfolios on medical students' learning during clinical clerkship. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Assess the effectiveness of reflective portfolios in enhancing self-directed learning and professional development among medical students. This includes evaluating the portfolio's ability to:
 - ◆ Identify personal strengths and weaknesses,
 - ◆ Promote critical thinking and reflection on clinical experiences,
 - ◆ Facilitate the development of clinical skills and decision-making abilities.
2. Explore the role of reflective portfolios in bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application in clinical settings. This includes examining the portfolio's effectiveness in:
 - ◆ Encouraging students to critically analyse their clinical encounters,
 - ◆ Fostering a deeper understanding of patient care and medical practice,
 - ◆ Promoting the development of a reflective mindset essential for lifelong learning.
3. Identify potential challenges and areas for improvement in the implementation of reflective portfolios in clinical clerkships. This includes examining:
 - ◆ The perceived time commitment and usability of the portfolio,
 - ◆ The effectiveness of feedback mechanisms and student preferences for feedback,
 - ◆ Potential opportunities for digitalization and standardization of reflective practices.

By addressing these aims, this study seeks to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on the use of reflective portfolios in medical education and provide valuable insights for optimizing their implementation to enhance student learning and prepare future physicians for the complexities of modern healthcare.

Literature review

Reflective practice and medical education

Reflective practice has long been recognized as a valuable tool in medical education. It encourages students to critically examine their experiences, evaluate their performance, and use these reflections to guide future actions (Boud, Keogh, and Walker, 1985). Its integration into medical training is grounded in adult learning theory, particularly the work of Knowles (1984), who emphasized self-directed learning as a core characteristic of adult learners. In this context, reflective practice helps students develop self-awareness, critical thinking, and adaptive behaviours essential for becoming competent healthcare professionals.

Reflective portfolios provide a structured framework for engaging with reflection. Typically, they include components for documenting clinical experiences, self-assessment, and feedback from supervisors (Dornan et al., 2005). Moon (2004) explains that such tools promote deep learning by requiring students to analyse their clinical encounters, identify areas for growth, and develop improvement strategies. Brookfield (1995) further supports that structured reflection encourages lifelong learning habits, as students are continuously prompted to evaluate and refine their professional practices.

In addition to supporting individual growth, reflective portfolios function as valuable assessment tools. Unlike traditional tests that assess knowledge at a single point in time, portfolios offer a longitudinal perspective on student development (Boud, 2013). This enables educators to provide targeted, formative feedback and evaluate students' progress in metacognition, self-regulation, and professional maturity, domains critical for future clinical competence.

Challenges in clinical education

Medical students often face significant challenges as they transition from theoretical instruction to hands-on clinical practice (Ackermann and Dijkers, 2016). This period is marked by steep learning curves and heightened anxiety, particularly when students lack consistent supervision or feedback (Monrouxe et al., 2014). Swanwick (2014) highlights that, without guided reflection or mentoring, students may struggle to apply knowledge effectively, compromising their confidence and clinical reasoning.

One persistent issue is the limited availability of clinical supervisors. Time constraints and patient care responsibilities often restrict supervisors' ability to offer real-time feedback and mentorship (Atkinson and Ajjawi, 2019). High student-to-patient ratios further exacerbate this problem, limiting opportunities for experiential learning (Visscher-Voerman et al., 1999).

These systemic limitations suggest the need for learning tools that facilitate self-assessment and independent learning.

Reflective portfolios can address these gaps by empowering students to monitor their own development. Even in the absence of direct supervision, reflective writing supports self-evaluation and internalization of lessons learned from clinical experiences (Driessen et al., 2007). Additionally, Boud, Keogh, and Walker (1985) argue that such tools promote proactive feedback-seeking, which can strengthen reflective depth and peer-supported learning.

The reflective portfolio in medical education

Reflective portfolios have been applied across numerous disciplines – including nursing, pharmacy, and social work – as a means of supporting professional development and reflective learning (Smith, 2011). In medical education, their use has grown substantially in recent years, with portfolios offering a structured mechanism to enhance critical reflection, self-assessment, and lifelong learning (Moon, 2008).

Evidence suggests that portfolios improve student competencies across cognitive and professional domains. They enhance self-awareness, critical thinking, and clinical decision making (Caldwell et al., 2016; Er et al., 2019; Zubair and Bilal, 2018). Greenaway (1995) highlights that by encouraging students to identify and address knowledge gaps, portfolios instil habits essential for lifelong learning. However, despite their promise, reflective portfolios often face resistance. Students and faculty cite concerns about time commitments and the difficulty of delivering timely, constructive feedback (Caldwell and Morley, 2012).

In response to these challenges, digital and online reflective portfolios (e-portfolios) have been increasingly adopted in medical curricula. These platforms support real-time data entry, remote access, multimedia integration, and automated progress tracking – features that are particularly attractive to the current generation of learners (Ackerman and Chappell, 2019; Chang et al., 2016). Digital portfolios also enhance feedback mechanisms, enabling asynchronous supervisor engagement and streamlined reflection cycles (Smith and Caldwell, 2012). Still, their successful implementation depends on adequate training, ease of use, and alignment with curricular outcomes (Driessen et al., 2007; Zubair and Bilal, 2018).

Reflective models in medical education

Reflective portfolios have been used in various fields of education, including nursing, pharmacy, and social work, to promote reflective practice and professional development (Smith, 2011). In medical education, reflective portfolios have gained traction as a valuable

tool for enhancing student learning and fostering professional growth. By providing a structured framework for reflection, portfolios encourage students to critically analyse their clinical experiences, identify learning gaps, and develop strategies for improvement (Moon, 2008). The use of reflective portfolios in medical education is supported by a growing body of evidence. Studies have shown that reflective portfolios can improve students' self-awareness, critical thinking, and clinical decision-making skills (Caldwell et al., 2016; Er et al., 2019; Zubair and Bilal, 2018). Additionally, reflective portfolios have been found to promote lifelong learning by encouraging students to continuously evaluate their performance and seek growth opportunities (Greenaway, 1995).

To support this process, several reflective models are commonly used in medical education. Among the most widely adopted is Gibbs' Reflective Cycle (Gibbs, 1988), which provides a six-stage structured approach: description, feelings, evaluation, analysis, conclusion, and action plan. Its simplicity and stepwise logic make it appealing for students and educators alike (Burton, 2000). Another influential model is Schön's Reflective Practice Framework (Schön, 1987), which distinguishes between reflection-in-action (during the activity) and reflection-on-action (after the activity), helping students evaluate decisions in real time and retrospectively (Smith, 2013). A third approach, Kolb's Experiential Learning Cycle, frames reflection within a continuous learning loop: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation (Kolb, 1984). Each of these models offers a different lens through which students can understand and enhance their clinical practice.

Despite their value, the varied application of these models across institutions has led to inconsistencies in reflective practice. Studies suggest that the lack of standardization in how reflection models are taught and applied can affect the quality and depth of students' reflective writing, as well as the effectiveness of feedback provided by supervisors (Caldwell and Morley, 2013; Zubair and Bilal, 2018). Standardizing reflective practices – whether by mandating the use of a particular model or offering structured guidance on model application – could improve the comparability of student reflections and ensure reflective learning is meaningful (Boud, 2013; Moon, 2013). For example, embedding model-based prompts within portfolio templates or offering faculty development on model-specific feedback can enhance consistency and learning outcomes.

This issue was observed in the present study where, although students were introduced to a comprehensive reflective portfolio, they were not required to follow a specific reflective model. Consequently, 53.8% of students reported using Gibbs' Reflective Cycle, while others employed Schön's model or no structured model at all. This mirrors broader trends in the literature, where the absence of explicit institutional policy leads to heterogeneous reflection quality.

Gibbs' Reflective Cycle

Gibbs' model remains the most widely used reflective framework in undergraduate medical education. Its structured format guides learners through six progressive stages – from initial description of a clinical event to planning future improvement. Its appeal lies in its clarity and ease of use, particularly for novice reflectors (Gibbs, 1988). However, some scholars argue that the model's formulaic nature may result in superficial reflections unless students are trained to apply deeper analytical thinking (Burton, 2000).

In the context of this study, the majority of students who used a reflective model selected Gibbs'. Its popularity likely stems from its practicality and alignment with medical curriculum templates. However, medical educators should encourage students to move beyond the checklist approach and engage in thoughtful, evaluative reflection. For instance, students can be prompted to explore the underlying causes of clinical decisions or consider alternative responses, thereby fostering higher-order cognitive engagement.

Figure 1: Gibbs' Reflective Cycle

Schön's Reflective Practice Model

Schön's model is uniquely suited to the clinical environment, where decisions often occur under time pressure. His distinction between reflection-in-action and reflection-on-action provides a dual framework for real-time and post-event reflection (Schön, 1987). This is especially relevant in emergency and acute-care contexts, where students must process and respond to complex information quickly. In this study, a smaller subset of students reported using Schön's model, suggesting its value may be underutilized in undergraduate teaching. Promoting this model through simulation-based teaching or reflective debriefs could improve its uptake.

Kolb's Experiential Learning Cycle

Kolb's model offers a dynamic loop linking experience to experimentation. The four stages – concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation – promote continuous improvement and behavioural adaptation (Kolb, 1984). In the setting of reflective portfolios, Kolb's model helps students not only reflect on what they have experienced but also to derive insights, formulate concepts, and test new approaches in future clinical encounters.

Ultimately, reflective portfolios can only fulfil their potential when embedded within consistent pedagogical frameworks. Without a clear model to guide the process, students may revert to superficial entries, and educators may find it difficult to provide meaningful feedback. Therefore, medical schools are encouraged to select, implement, and train faculty and students in the use of a standardized reflective model. Both Moon (2004) and Boud (2013) emphasize that structured reflection increases learner engagement and optimizes the educational value of portfolios.

In summary, while multiple models of reflection can add richness and flexibility to portfolio-based learning, the evidence strongly supports the case for consistency, clear guidance, and institutional support. Reflective models such as those of Gibbs, Schön, and Kolb, when systematically applied, offer powerful tools for fostering critical thinking, clinical competence, and professional identity formation in medical education.

Methodology

Study design and context

This was a cross-sectional, mixed-methods study conducted at the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, University of Mauritius, during the 2022-2023 academic year. The research focused on evaluating student perceptions of a newly implemented reflective portfolio during

clinical clerkships in internal medicine and otorhinolaryngology rotations. The study assessed students' subjective experiences and views of the portfolio's usefulness, rather than its direct impact on academic performance or clinical outcomes.

Mauritius, as a Small Island Developing State, faces systemic challenges in clinical education, including high student-to-patient ratios and limited supervision due to workforce constraints. These challenges provided the rationale for introducing a structured reflective tool that could support students' learning and self-assessment, even in under-resourced environments.

Development and implementation of the reflective portfolio

To assess the impact of reflective portfolios on medical students' learning, a comprehensive reflective portfolio was developed and implemented during clinical clerkships. The portfolio was specifically designed by the authors, a team of clinical educators and medical education researchers at the University of Mauritius, for the dual purpose of conducting this study and integrating the tool into the undergraduate MBBS curriculum.

The development process included:

- ◆ Consultations with senior academic and clinical faculty,
- ◆ Alignment with existing course learning outcomes,
- ◆ Pilot testing among a small group of students to ensure contextual relevance, usability, and clarity.

The portfolio was implemented in the Department of Medicine and targeted 4th-, 5th-, and 6th-year undergraduate students enrolled in clinical clerkships. It was tailored to address known challenges in the local setting, such as high caseloads, inconsistent feedback, and time constraints.

The reflective portfolio included three structured components.

- ◆ **Mini-Clinical Evaluation Exercises (mini-CEX):** for formative assessment of clinical and communication skills during patient encounters.
- ◆ **Direct Observation of Procedural Skills (DOPS):** for assessing technical skills and procedural competence with feedback.
- ◆ **Reflective Writing Sections:** requiring students to analyse clinical experiences, identify learning needs, and set improvement goals.

Compared to unstructured narrative reflections, this tool integrates structured assessment and reflective learning, drawing on best practices from Gibbs' Reflective Cycle and other experiential learning frameworks.

To ensure effective uptake, orientation workshops were held for both students and faculty. These workshops provided guidance on:

- ◆ The purpose and benefits of reflective portfolios,
- ◆ Strategies for reflective writing and self-assessment,
- ◆ Giving and receiving feedback constructively.

The reflective portfolio was implemented over one full academic year, from August 2022 to July 2023, across the clinical clerkship rotations in the Department of Medicine at the University of Mauritius. It was piloted with 4th-, 5th-, and 6th-year undergraduate medical students during their respective clinical placements. To evaluate the effectiveness and student experience of the portfolio, a structured online survey was conducted in July 2023 following the completion of clinical postings. The survey was disseminated through institutional email channels and was available for three weeks. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants. The survey included both Likert-scale and open-ended items, and responses were collected anonymously.

Figure 2: Flowchart of the reflective portfolio process in clinical clerkships

Survey of student perceptions

At the end of the academic year, a structured, anonymous survey was administered to evaluate students' perceptions of the reflective portfolio. The survey aimed to explore:

- ◆ Perceived usefulness of the portfolio in supporting learning,
- ◆ Impact on self-directed learning and professional development,
- ◆ Usability of portfolio components,
- ◆ Challenges encountered and recommendations for improvement.

The survey instrument included:

- ◆ 12 closed-ended Likert-scale items (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree),
- ◆ 3 open-ended qualitative questions.

The tool was piloted among five students for face validity and clarity, with minor revisions made prior to full rollout. A copy of the final survey instrument is included in Appendix A1.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the University of Mauritius Research Ethics Committee. The study was conducted in accordance with institutional ethical guidelines, and all participants provided informed consent. The ethics clearance reference number is RDP/jb/UoMREC45/18 April 2022.

Data collection and analysis

Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, frequencies). Qualitative responses were analysed thematically using an inductive approach to identify key insights, challenges, and recommendations.

Participant characteristics

A total of 52 undergraduate medical students participated in the survey.

- ◆ **Year of Study:** 28.8% fourth year, 36.5% fifth year, 34.6% sixth year
- ◆ **Gender:** 63.5% female, 36.5% male
- ◆ **Nationality:** 92% Mauritian, 8% international (mostly from the SADC region)
- ◆ **Age Range:** 22-26 years (mean age: 23.4 years)

These students belong to Generation Z, a cohort characterized by digital fluency, preference for self-paced learning, and strong value on personal development and feedback. These traits align with the portfolio's objectives and may explain the generally positive student engagement observed in this study. As recent literature suggests, Gen Z learners benefit from structured reflection tools that enable real-time feedback and self-improvement (Imagine Johns Hopkins, 2022).

Furthermore, the institutional ethos of the University of Mauritius, emphasizing reflective practice, self-directed learning, and ethical professional behaviour, may have positively influenced how students engaged with the reflective portfolio.

Results

Participant demographics and context

A total of 52 undergraduate medical students participated in the survey at the end of the 2022-2023 academic year, following the implementation of the reflective portfolio in clinical clerkships. The sample comprised 28.8% Year 4 students, 36.5% Year 5 students, and 34.6% Year 6 students. Most of the students (57.7%) were assigned to internal medicine rotations, while 42.3% were placed in otorhinolaryngology. No participants were allocated to paediatrics, psychiatry, obstetrics, or gynaecology departments during the study period. The average age of respondents was 23.4 years, with 63.5% identifying as female and 92% as Mauritian nationals. These demographics are representative of Generation Z learners, whose educational preferences typically include structured feedback, self-paced reflection, and purpose-driven learning experiences.

Objective 1: Perceptions of the portfolio's impact on personal development

Students generally perceived the reflective portfolio as a valuable tool for supporting personal insight and development. The statement 'The portfolio helped me identify my weaknesses' received one of the highest agreement ratings, with a mean score of 4.19 (SD = 0.92) and 85% of students agreeing. Likewise, the statement 'The portfolio helped me identify my strengths' received a mean score of 4.10 (SD = 1.21), supported by 78% agreement. One student commented: 'It made me realize that I tend to focus too much on the diagnosis and neglect communication. I am now working on balancing both.' Another stated: 'Seeing my progress in writing helped me understand my strengths in patient rapport, which I used to underestimate.'

However, the reflective process also had mixed emotional outcomes. The item ‘The portfolio improved my self-esteem’ received the lowest average score ($M = 3.40$, $SD = 1.05$), with only 68% agreement. Some students reported that while reflection increased self-awareness, it also brought insecurities to light. One student noted: ‘It was useful, but sometimes I ended up feeling more insecure after writing things down.’ Another shared: ‘The portfolio showed me what I still had to learn, motivating, but also a bit daunting.’

Objective 2: Perceived impact on professional development

The highest-rated survey item overall was ‘The portfolio helped me identify my clinical skills’, which achieved a mean score of 4.46 ($SD = 0.85$), with 92% of students agreeing. This was closely followed by ‘The portfolio helped me identify knowledge gaps’, which had a mean of 4.30 ($SD = 1.09$) and 86% agreement. One respondent reflected: ‘It made me realize how much more I needed to learn about physical exams. I focused my next rotation on improving this.’

Students also found value in the structured elements of the portfolio that supported their professional learning. Reflective writing received a score of 4.08 ($SD = 0.93$), and the DOPS component, which assessed procedural skills, was rated at 4.00 ($SD = 0.87$). The mini-CEX, which focused on communication during clinical interactions, was also well received with a mean score of 4.05 ($SD = 0.91$). These scores indicate that students found the structured components of the portfolio both practical and supportive of their clinical skill development.

Objective 3: Portfolio usability and educational relevance

In terms of usability, students reported that the portfolio was accessible and intuitive. The statement ‘The portfolio was easy to use and understand’ received a mean score of 4.00 ($SD = 0.90$). Furthermore, the majority of students indicated that they would recommend the use of reflective portfolios to future cohorts, with this item receiving a mean score of 4.25 ($SD = 0.86$).

The portfolio also appeared to foster a culture of feedback and improvement. Students reported that it motivated them to seek feedback from their supervisors ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.84$) and that the feedback they received was constructive and useful ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 0.88$). These findings suggest that the tool encouraged students not only to reflect on their own performance but also to engage in meaningful dialogue with faculty and supervisors.

Visual summary of key findings

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for each of the 12 Likert-scale items used in the student perception survey. These results reflect students' evaluation of the reflective portfolio's educational value, usability, and impact on clinical learning and development.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Survey Items (N = 52)

Survey Statement	Mean (M)	SD	Agreement (%)
1. The portfolio helped me identify my clinical strengths.	4.10	1.21	78%
2. The portfolio helped me identify my clinical weaknesses.	4.19	0.92	85%
3. The portfolio improved my self-esteem.	3.40	1.05	68%
4. The portfolio encouraged me to become a self-directed learner.	4.18	0.90	82%
5. The mini-CEX was helpful in improving my clinical communication.	4.05	0.91	81%
6. The DOPS component helped me improve procedural skills.	4.00	0.87	78%
7. Reflective writing helped me analyse and understand my clinical experiences better.	4.08	0.93	80%
8. The portfolio motivated me to seek feedback from my supervisors.	4.12	0.84	83%
9. The feedback I received through the portfolio was constructive and useful.	4.02	0.88	80%
10. Completing the portfolio helped me identify gaps in my clinical knowledge.	4.30	1.09	86%
11. The portfolio was easy to use and understand.	4.00	0.90	76%
12. I would recommend the use of reflective portfolios for future cohorts.	4.25	0.86	84%

Figure 3 illustrates student perceptions of the portfolio's impact across five core domains: identification of strengths (78%), recognition of weaknesses (85%), professional development (92%), improved self-esteem (68%), and identification of knowledge gaps (86%). This visual representation underscores the portfolio's strong influence on critical learning and professional awareness, with more modest gains reported in personal confidence.

Figure 3: Student perceptions of the reflective portfolio's impact across five domains

This chart displays the percentage of students who agreed that the portfolio helped them identify their strengths (78%), recognize their weaknesses (85%), develop professionally (92%), improve self-esteem (68%), and identify knowledge gaps (86%). The data illustrate the portfolio's overall positive effect on both personal insight and professional growth, with comparatively lower influence on self-esteem. A detailed tabulated summary of all Likert-scale survey responses, including mean scores and standard deviations, is shown in Table 1. As illustrated in Figure 3, students reported high levels of agreement regarding the portfolio's value in professional development (92%), identification of knowledge gaps (86%), and recognition of weaknesses (85%). The mean score for professional development was $M = 4.21$, $SD = 0.57$, while personal development scored $M = 3.84$, $SD = 0.88$. Students found that the portfolio enhanced self-awareness: 'It made me realize that I tend to focus too much on the diagnosis and neglect communication. I am now working on balancing both.' Some also recognized new strengths: 'Seeing my progress in writing helped me understand my strengths in patient rapport, which I used to underestimate.' However, the item on self-esteem received the lowest rating ($M=3.40$, $SD = 1.05$, 68% agreement), with students noting that reflection sometimes exposed insecurities: 'It was useful, but sometimes I ended up feeling more insecure after writing things down.' The highest rated item overall was the identification of clinical skills ($M = 4.46$, $SD = 0.85$), followed by knowledge gaps ($M = 4.30$, $SD = 1.09$), confirming the reflective portfolio's role in enhancing both awareness and application of clinical competencies.

Figure 4 provides a visual synthesis of the major thematic findings across all objectives, categorizing perceived strengths and weaknesses of the portfolio based on student responses and observed outcomes.

Figure 4: Key findings from the reflective portfolio study, summarizing impacts across domains

Figure 4 provides a visual synthesis of the reflective portfolio’s educational value as perceived by undergraduate medical students. It distils the key domains explored through the survey: personal development, professional learning, usability, and reflective capacity. The strongest impacts were observed in areas related to clinical skills, identification of knowledge gaps, and motivation for feedback seeking, all of which support the portfolio’s role in promoting professional growth and lifelong learning behaviours.

In contrast, while personal insight was developed, improvements in self-esteem were comparatively modest, indicating that deeper reflection may sometimes evoke discomfort or self-doubt. The usability of the portfolio was also positively rated, suggesting that students found the tool accessible and relevant to their clinical training context. These findings reinforce the value of reflective portfolios in competency-based medical education and underscore the importance of structured reflection as part of undergraduate medical curricula, particularly in resource-constrained settings like SIDS.

Tabulated summary of results

A detailed breakdown of all survey responses, including mean scores and standard deviations for each of the twelve Likert-scale items, is available in Appendix A2. These quantitative results support the conclusion that students perceived the reflective portfolio as an effective tool for enhancing self-directed learning, promoting professional development, and guiding meaningful reflection during clinical clerkships.

Discussion

Fostering self-directed learning

The findings of this study suggest that reflective portfolios are valuable tools for fostering self-directed learning in medical education. By encouraging students to critically analyse their clinical experiences, the portfolio helped them develop a deeper understanding of their strengths and weaknesses, enabling them to take ownership of their learning. This aligns with the principles of adult learning theory, which emphasizes the importance of self-direction and internal motivation in personal and professional growth (Knowles, 1984; Moon, 2004).

Moreover, the portfolio encouraged continuous learning by enabling students to identify learning gaps and develop strategies to address them. This is particularly evident in the students' capacity to reflect on diagnostic reasoning, interpersonal communication, and knowledge application. The enhanced self-awareness reported by participants aligns with previous research indicating that reflection strengthens professional identity and intrinsic motivation (Boud, Keogh and Walker, 1985; Mann, Gordon and MacLeod, 2009).

Encouraging critical thinking and clinical decision making

While the reflective portfolio had a positive impact on students' professional development and self-awareness, its effect on higher-order thinking skills such as critical thinking and clinical decision making was less prominent. Although students reported that reflection improved their recognition of clinical gaps, the development of complex reasoning and diagnostic deliberation seemed limited. Critical thinking in medical education requires learners to navigate diagnostic ambiguity, interpret conflicting data, and evaluate treatment options, skills that go beyond personal insight and benefit from peer discussion, mentorship, and active problem-solving contexts.

This suggests that while reflective portfolios serve as strong foundations for awareness, they should be paired with case-based learning, team-based discussions, or simulation exercises to strengthen cognitive flexibility and judgement. Embedding structured reflection within interactive clinical learning environments may help bridge this gap.

Bridging theory and practice

One of the key strengths of the reflective portfolio observed in this study was its ability to help students bridge the gap between classroom learning and real-world clinical application. Students reported that reflecting on daily clinical encounters helped them internalize theoretical knowledge and integrate it into their decision-making processes. This aligns with experiential learning theory, which holds that active engagement and post-experience reflection enhance knowledge retention and practical competence (Kolb, 1984).

The portfolio thus functioned as both a cognitive scaffold and a motivational tool, helping students understand the relevance of what they learned and how to improve in real time. In resource-constrained clinical settings, where direct supervision may be sporadic, such tools can offer structured opportunities for continuous self-improvement.

Comparative insights: Relevance and application in Seychelles

While this study focused on clinical education in Mauritius, there is strong potential for adapting reflective portfolios to the Seychellois context. Given Seychelles' reliance on foreign-trained doctors and the absence of a fully-localized medical-education system, reflective portfolios could be instrumental in fostering contextualized learning and smooth integration into the national health system. Returning Seychellois students, trained abroad, often face challenges adapting to local clinical environments. Reflective portfolios may facilitate this transition by helping them understand and document differences in patient expectations, health system operations, and communication norms.

Additionally, Seychelles' heavy dependence on expatriate health workers highlights another application: portfolios could be used as orientation and integration tools for foreign doctors. Through structured reflection, these professionals could critically examine how their previous training applies, or doesn't, in the local context, helping accelerate professional adaptation and culturally sensitive practice.

Beyond medicine, the reflective portfolio framework can be expanded to allied health, nursing, and midwifery education, especially as health training expands within UniSey. In-service and on-the-job training in public health or even non-health disciplines could benefit

from this approach, encouraging reflective learning among adult learners in continuing professional development contexts.

Digitalization and the role of AI in reflective practice

The growing call for a mobile or digital version of the reflective portfolio, supported by 27.5% of students, reflects a broader trend towards digital transformation in medical education. A mobile platform could allow real-time documentation, automatic feedback prompts, supervisor alerts, and data analytics for longitudinal progress tracking. Digital portfolios would also improve usability and reduce administrative burdens, as students often cited time as a limiting factor.

Looking ahead, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in medical education opens new avenues for portfolio evolution. AI-powered tools could be embedded into digital portfolios to offer personalized prompts for deeper reflection, adaptive feedback based on previous entries, and sentiment analysis to identify students in need of support. In clinical training, where AI is increasingly used for diagnostic decision support, reflective portfolios could help students critically evaluate the interplay between machine recommendations and human judgment.

Importantly, this raises new pedagogical questions: How should medical students be trained to reflect on clinical decision making when AI systems are involved? What is the role of the physician in the AI-augmented care process? Reflective portfolios may be one of the few tools that encourage students to question and articulate their evolving professional identity in an AI-integrated environment – an area ripe for further investigation.

Challenges and areas for improvement

Despite their educational value, several barriers to portfolio use were highlighted by participants. Chief among them was the time commitment required to maintain reflective entries during clinical rotations. Students also expressed concern about delays in receiving supervisor feedback – an essential component of meaningful reflection. Furthermore, preferences for feedback modalities varied, with some students preferring written comments and others favouring verbal feedback. This suggests the need for hybrid feedback models and time-saving mechanisms, which a digital portfolio could easily support.

Figure 5: Student feedback preferences

As mentioned previously, inconsistency in the use of reflective models remains a challenge. While the portfolio was structured, students were free to use models of their choice. This led to variability in depth, clarity, and evaluability of reflections. Programmes may consider mandating one or two reflective models, e.g., Gibbs’ cycle or Schön’s model, and aligning training around their use to support comparability and supervisor guidance.

Standardizing reflective practices

Standardization remains critical for ensuring consistency in student reflection and supervisor feedback. While this study implemented a structured reflective portfolio with predefined components, students varied in their use of reflective frameworks. A significant portion (53.8%) used Gibbs’ model, while others adopted different or no formal structures. This inconsistency may lead to unequal learning outcomes and difficulty in providing targeted feedback.

To address this, medical faculties should offer clear guidelines on reflective models to be used and provide exemplar entries. Faculty training is equally essential to ensure that feedback given is constructive, timely, and based on observable competencies. Standardization does not imply rigid conformity but rather alignment of principles, frameworks, and evaluation criteria.

Future research directions

This study opens several avenues for future research. Comparative implementation studies could explore the reflective portfolio's effectiveness across SIDS contexts such as Seychelles, Comoros, and the Maldives. Longitudinal studies could examine how reflective habits persist into internship or specialist training. Evaluating the integration of AI features into digital portfolios and how they influence learning, confidence, and professional identity formation is another promising area. Additionally, research on the role of portfolios in ethical reflection, interprofessional collaboration, and health systems adaptation could broaden their utility beyond clinical skills development.

Conclusion

The implementation of reflective portfolios in clinical clerkships has demonstrated their potential to promote self-directed learning and professional development among medical students. Reflective portfolios provide a structured mechanism for students to reflect on their clinical experiences, identify learning gaps, and develop strategies for improvement. While the portfolio was effective in fostering self-awareness and professional growth, its impact on critical thinking and clinical decision making was less pronounced, highlighting the need for complementary educational interventions.

A comparative reflection with the Seychelles context further emphasizes the utility of reflective portfolios in small island states where clinical education faces similar challenges. Both Mauritius and Seychelles experience high student-to-patient ratios and limited supervision, making self-directed learning tools such as reflective portfolios even more valuable. The introduction of digital reflective portfolios in Seychelles could enhance usability and feedback mechanisms, especially given the more limited healthcare workforce there. The ability to provide real-time feedback and foster continuous reflection through digital platforms presents a promising opportunity for Seychelles to strengthen its clinical education framework.

The challenges identified in this study, including time constraints and delays in feedback, underscore the importance of improving the usability and efficiency of reflective portfolios in both Mauritius and Seychelles. The transition to digital platforms presents a promising opportunity to address these challenges by streamlining the documentation process, enhancing feedback mechanisms, and enabling real-time access to reflections and assessments.

To maximize the educational value of reflective portfolios, medical schools should consider standardizing reflective practices and providing students with clear guidelines and training on how to engage in meaningful reflection. Incorporating structured frameworks such as Gibbs' Reflective Cycle, Schön's Reflective Practice Model, and Kolb's Experiential Learning Cycle can provide students with practical tools to guide their reflections. Ultimately, reflective portfolios should form part of a broader range of educational strategies that include case-based learning, simulation, mentoring, and digital tools, to foster well-rounded, contextually sensitive, and reflective healthcare professionals.

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Appendix A1: Full survey instrument

Undergraduate Medical Students' Perception of the Educational Value of a Reflective Portfolio during the Implementation Phase, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, University of Mauritius, Academic Year: 2022–2023

Section 1: Demographic information

Please tick or fill in the appropriate response.

Year of study:

Year 4 Year 5 Year 6

Gender:

Male Female Prefer not to say

Age:

____ years

Nationality:

Mauritian Non-Mauritian (please specify): _____

Section 2: Perceptions of the educational value of the reflective portfolio

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with each statement.

Likert Scale:

1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree

Survey Item	1	2	3	4	5
The portfolio helped me identify my clinical strengths.					
The portfolio helped me identify my clinical weaknesses.					
The portfolio improved my self-confidence.					
The portfolio encouraged me to become a self-directed learner.					
The mini-CEX was helpful in improving my clinical communication					
The DOPS component helped me improve procedural skills.					
Reflective writing helped me analyse and understand my clinical experiences better.					
The portfolio motivated me to seek feedback from my supervisors.					

The feedback I received through the portfolio was constructive and useful.					
Completing the portfolio helped me identify gaps in my clinical knowledge.					
The portfolio was easy to use and understand					
I would recommend the use of reflective portfolios for future cohorts.					

Section 3: Open-ended questions

What did you find most helpful about the reflective portfolio?

What were the biggest challenges you faced while completing the portfolio?

Do you have any suggestions for improving the design or implementation of the portfolio?

Appendix A2: Tabulated survey results by objective

This table presents descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) for each survey item aligned with the study's objectives, assessing student perceptions of the reflective portfolio's educational value.

Survey Item	Mean	Standard Deviation
The portfolio helped me identify my clinical strengths.	4.10	1.21
The portfolio helped me identify my clinical weaknesses.	4.19	0.92
The portfolio improved my self-esteem.	3.40	1.05
The portfolio encouraged me to become a self-directed learner.	4.00	0.89
The mini-CEX was helpful in improving my clinical communication.	4.05	0.91
The DOPS component helped me improve procedural skills.	4.00	0.87
Reflective writing helped me analyse and understand my clinical experiences better.	4.08	0.93
The portfolio motivated me to seek feedback from my supervisors.	4.12	0.84
The feedback I received through the portfolio was constructive and useful.	4.02	0.88
Completing the portfolio helped me identify gaps in my clinical knowledge.	4.30	1.09
The portfolio was easy to use and understand.	4.00	0.90
I would recommend the use of reflective portfolios for future cohorts.	4.25	0.86